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CRITICAL ARTICLES

Culture, Multicultural and the Case of India

Sudhir K. Arora

Human culture, which determines the growth of a nation, is itself an outcome of a vision and art of living. Social, economic and political ingredients prepare the environment that shapes the attitude of the people. The growth of a human being in the given environment demonstrates the graph of a culture. Culture, which gives an identity to people, differs from group to group. Cultural growth is not simply an individual growth but a community growth. Societies, which vary in beliefs, customs, values, structure, policies and visions, have different cultures. Though the people are basically same physically, they differ because of a unique personality. Culture becomes a cementing force in binding them together into “a group sharing a certain degree of similarity, overcoming individual differences while setting us apart from other groups” (*The Human Portrait* 88). Hence, it binds the people in group and also differentiates from other groups.

Culture is a comprehensive term to the extent that it is often misunderstood and wrongly used. Even today, the definition given by Tylor is worth-mentioning. Tyler defines culture “as that complex whole which includes knowledge, beliefs, art, morals, law, customs, and any other capabilities and habits acquired by man as a members of society” (qtd. in *The Human Portrait* 88). Hence, he believes that culture is acquired or learned from the members of their group through the process of socialization that includes physical and mental aspects. It cannot be an individual phenomenon; rather it is a group one. In plain words, culture is “a way of life that is common to a group of people, including a collection of beliefs and attitudes, shared understandings, and patterns of behaviour that allow those people to live together in relative harmony, but set them apart from other peoples” (*The Human Portrait* 110).

Culture brings refinement and excellence in life. Notwithstanding its categorization into regional culture, national culture, society culture,

Hindu culture, Muslim Culture, global culture etc., it possesses some universal ingredients which become keys to the basic solutions to the problems of living. Human welfare is ever present in the roots of every culture. Embracing the good things from others for the sake of human welfare is the sign that makes a culture living. Any culture that opposes changes and follows the path which does not take man to progress, peace and prosperity is no culture at all. Indian culture is dynamic not because it is Indian but because of its adaptable and assimilative nature to the changes. If it had not adopted what is good, it would have decayed earlier. Positive approach, tolerance and the ability to assimilate what is good are some ingredients that make a culture alive. Matthew Arnold, for whom, "the pursuit of perfection, then, is the pursuit of sweetness and light" believes that "He who works for sweetness works in the end for light also. He who works for light works in the end of sweetness also. But, he who works for sweetness and light united, works to make reason and the will of God prevail" (47). The concept of providing an environment of happiness and welfare all around can be an outcome of a cultured mind that thinks of bright and peaceful future.

Culture is often misunderstood as civilization. It is culture that provides the foundations to any civilization. Culture contributes to the inner growth while civilization to material growth. Culture with motivational force instills an ability to invent in man who invents and, hence, contributes in making civilization rich. Civilization is what a man invents while culture is his ability to invent. Culture, the abstract makes civilization, the concrete. The abstract culture makes a man think to the extent that he develops means that makes the building of civilization. Language, an ability to communicate creates culture which, in the long run gives birth to civilization. The foundation makes the building strong and durable. The cultural intellectual makeup prepares the civilized path for social development.

Diversity is now not a negative concept; rather it has become more popular than ever in its new form of multiculturalism. Though it is sometimes misused or overused for people with more than one culture, it is a right term for respecting and promoting multiple cultures. Respecting and acknowledging the differences or diversities create an environment for healthy relationship among the people of various groups. Multiculturalism does not force to cook various ingredients in order to turn them into one kind of food. Rather, each ingredient seems to have its own uniqueness. Its uniqueness is its beauty. Language

communicates; communication makes interaction possible with different cultures resulting in acknowledging the differences which finally give birth to multiculturalism. The concept of multiculturalism is favoured not because of diversities but because of its being a possible way of protecting the local culture of a particular place or nation which certainly be a promoting factor in making the global cultural diversity rich and safe. Two cultures come together and get in touch through a contact region which provides circumstances for learning from each other's ideologies oriented by culture. Cultural diversity is not a sin; rather it has become a virtue. One can learn what is best in other cultures and leave what clashes with the basic cultural structure. Multiculturalism provides multiple approaches to life and vision and helps in understanding the extremes—cultural interface and cultural seclusion. It does not believe wholly that race, religion and caste create culture. But, the champions of multiculturalism argue that culture is the consequence of multiple ingredients which vary with the variations in the global world. They also consider multiculturalism as the best way for maintaining the concept of egalitarianism. What translates justice into reality is not the yardstick from one culture but cultural communications via dialogues among multiple cultures. The magic is done by the idea of multiculturalism which offers possibilities to several different cultures for coexisting peacefully and fairly.

No doubt, the concept of multiculturalism seems to be alluring and protective if it is put into practice. But, some fanatics who are not in its favour perform destruction and torture the people other than their culture. Such narrow minded people certainly obstruct the path of culture that aims at welfare of the people. That everyone is ethnocentric more or less has somewhere a grain of truth. This love for one's culture in preference to other culture can be seen in the over praise of their myths, folk tales, proverbs and also language. To love one's culture is not bad but to think other cultures bad or inferior is not justified from any angle. People should be broad-minded and catholic in appreciating positive ingredients in other cultures. It is true that morals and values are based on the culture that people live and embrace but to judge other cultures on the basis of their set parameters is not fair. Cultural shock is felt when a man leaves his own culture and embraces another. He oscillates between the two cultures and feels frustration not only because of the clash of the old values with the new ones but also because of the attitude towards solutions to the problems which vary from one culture

to another. Differences concerning behavioural practices, norms and morals give each culture its uniqueness. The differences add beauty to every culture in one way or other. But, ethnocentrism present somewhere in man makes him a bit partial to his own culture to the extent that he feels that anyone who does not follow his culture or departs from the ways of his culture is a queer.

Indian culture, in spite of being influenced by the modern means of living and life-style, remains unchanged in her basic structure, No doubt, people may change their styles in clothing, eating and living but will never be away from Indian values and traditions which are deeply rooted in their heart, mind, body and soul. Spiritualism is the life breath of Indian culture. People search for solutions of their problems in spiritualism and have firm faith in cosmopolitanism. The myth, folk-tales and rich past are the archetypes before them. The action plan with the united effort is the very characteristic of the Indian people who fight against injustice. Patience and tolerance are the mantras in the reign of Indian culture. Even the foreign language is given the native touches. De-colonizing of English is being done by the Indian authors who either writing in English or in any other language are successfully propagating the Indian Culture to the West. Indian culture is not confined to any individual but is the result of totality of group ways, thoughts and action as accepted and followed by a group of people. The rich heritage of customs, traditions, values, beliefs, spiritualism and the mind-set is a legacy of the past which differentiates Indians from other groups.

Indian culture is distinctive in itself because of its rich tradition and values that follow the goal of *Satyam*, *Shivam* and *Sundaram*. Being secular in spirit, Indian culture with the feeling of cosmopolitanism has become human culture. Indian culture is based on the mantra of:

Sarve Bhavantu Sukhinah,
Sarve Santu Niraamayah,
Sarve Bhadraani Pashyantu,
Maa Kashchid Dukhabhaavbhaveta,
Om Shanthi Shanthi Shanthi. (“Shanti Mantras”)

Indian culture talks of the well-being of all without confining to a particular place. It longs for happiness, health and well-being of all the people. As it is broad in approach and catholic in vision, it considers the whole world its family. It promotes peace everywhere and invokes God for leading people from unreal to the real, darkness to light and death to immortality. The *Shanti mantra* reflects its character:

Om Aasto ma sat gamaya
Tamaso ma jyotir gamaya
mrityor ma amritam gamaya

Om Shanti Shanti Shantihi. (“Shanti Mantras”)

Gayatri Mantra: “*Om Bhur, Bhuvah, Svaha / Tat Savitur Vareniam / Bhargo Devasya Dhimahi / Dhiyo Yo Nah Prachodayat*” (Omnipresent Lord, Most worthy of worship / We meditate you / Remove our ignorance / And illuminate our minds) is chanted by Indians who get inner illumination and feel contentment. The spiritual character of Indian culture makes people grow inwardly. People treat their guest as god, respect elders, consider others as equal, become helpful to others in need, develop co-operation and high level of tolerance, multiply joy and happiness, share pain, embrace the Yoga and do their best to make the world a better place for all. Secularism flows in its veins. Though joint family system is the mantra that it chants, it has not denied the possibility of nuclear family in the changed circumstances. Dance and rituals are its part and parcel.

‘Unity in Diversity’ is the thread that binds all the people in India resulting in one composite culture—Indian Culture. Indian culture is considered to be a composite one because of her consisting of separate interconnected parts. All parts are somewhere connected resulting into a conceptual whole. But, recently some intellectuals have interrogated her composite character as they trace out multiculturalism in India. They argue that in India there is not one composite culture but several different cultures, which are coexisting successfully because of secular Indian spirit. Indian culture includes all—Tribal culture, Hindu Culture, Muslim culture, Jain culture, Buddhist culture, Christian culture, culture based on big cities like Mumbai culture, Delhite Culture, Bangali culture and the long list goes on. The question arises here: Are they really part of Indian culture? Or do they have Indian culture? Certainly they have their separate identities. When they have their identity, how can they be a part? They cannot assimilate their identity with others. Attempts have always been made but finally resulted in their recognition. Assimilation among them is possible to some extent but complete assimilation is a dream. The concept of composite culture is a way to bind all cultures into one while the reality seems to be different. Local culture never leaves its identity. If it leaves, how can it survive? All cultures struggle for their existence. Hence, they celebrate their identities, do their best to keep their uniqueness and become interconnected with

the concept of Indian culture without losing their basic structures. If minutely observed, the whole exercise leads to the way to multiculturalism. In India, theoretically there is one composite Indian culture but practically the waves of multiculturalism flow. The term, 'Multiculturalism,' is new one to Indians who, rather, use 'Diversity.' But, how far 'Diversity' differs from or equals to 'Multiculturalism' is a question worth-considering.

The concept of global culture once again has voted for the celebration of all cultures which differ from country to country or region to region but on macro level they contribute to one global culture. When one talks of country, the concept of Indian culture arises. But, when one talks of global culture, the concept of Indian culture gives place to culture of India. Again, Indian culture and culture of India differ as Muslim culture differs from culture of Muslim or Hindu culture from culture of Hindu or Christian culture from culture of Christian. It creates confusion because when concepts like Muslim culture or culture of Muslim are discussed, one fails to understand whether it is of Indian Muslim or Muslim residing anywhere in the world. Without making further confusion, it is better to confine to the theoretically concept of Indian culture which has roots in Hindu religion for its broad outlook, vision and the feeling of cosmopolitanism. There is one commonality in Indian culture in spite of different languages, religions, arts, literatures, customs and architectures. Tolerance and secularism bind all into one thread giving the form of unity in diversity. In comparison of European importance to reason, beauty, utility, pleasures and material welfare—the ingredients which serve body, Indian culture recognizes spirit and considers life to be psychological and spiritual. Man is a spirit that includes life and body. As he is a spirit, he is capable of being a god. For Westerners, man's reasoning mind and will power can make him better than what God has made him. They never consider that man is capable of becoming a God and people who think so live in illusion which is created out of their barbaric ignorance and arrogance.

Aurobindo considers "philosophy and religion" to be "the soul of Indian culture, inseparable from each other and interpenetrative" (55). He stresses that the main objective of Indian philosophy is "the knowledge of the spirit, the experience of it and the right way to a spiritual existence" (55). He pleads to search for the founts of native power in oneself in order to draw "deeper, more vital and fresher streams of the power of life than from anything the West can offer" (34). Indian

culture considers the growth and evolution of the spirit to be the main goal for which life is lived. Hence, it values architecture, sculpture and painting as they appeal the spirit through the eye.

Indian culture is spiritual to the core. Mysticism is India's invaluable heritage that believes in the concept of oneness in the entire creation, offers the message of *satyam*, *shivam* and *sundaram* to make man's life worth-living and commends the paths of knowledge (*jnana*), work (*karma*) and devotion (*bhakti*) that will take him to the gate of divine love which showers the spiritual delight—a stage of *ananda* that finally takes to the stage of *satchidananda*. The mystic, after following the eight steps—*yama*, *niyama*, *asana*, *pranayama*, *pratyahara*, *dharana*, *dhyana* and *samadhi*, makes himself entitled for attaining unitary consciousness. To realize the Divine, he crosses the *jaग्रat*, *svapna*, *susupt* and *turiya* states and feels His presence in soul, nature and the whole universe. For him, the world seems to be transitory. Hence, he releases himself from the *samsara*, the cycle of birth and rebirth in order to enter the state of bliss—*nirvana*. The main sources that make Indian culture spiritually rich are *Vedas*, *Upanishands* and, *Smritis*, *Darshans*, *Puranas*, the *Ramayan*, the *Mahabharata* and the *Bhagwad Gita* etc.

India is not simply a geographical land. It is much more than that. Assimilation and synthesis are her two virtues that make her alive despite of many races, tribes, languages, religions and creeds. Cultural synthesis is in her blood. Spirituality is her life-breath. Yoga is her strength. The figure of the cosmic dance of Shiva is her symbol that reveals the concept of creation, preservation and destruction. Though the Western culture has embraced her body closely, her spirit remains untouched. The concept of composite culture is yielding place to the light of multiculturalism which values the uniqueness of different cultures and traditions. The western storm, no doubt, has shaken the leaves of Indian culture but failed to destroy its roots which are firm and strong in their spiritual foundation. The spirit of tolerance and cosmopolitanism (*vasudev kutumbakum*), already includes the concept of multiculturalism in itself. Indian culture is now on the way to adapt itself to the new global environment that prefers the metaphor of “salad bowl” to the metaphor of “cooking pot.” India which is known as Hindustan or Bharat is not simply a country but Bharat Mata, the mother who has fostered a continuous and uninterrupted civilization “for about five thousand years of known and partly recorded history.” She is not

to be judged by the weaknesses of a few centuries but by her long history of establishment and accomplishment. “A culture,” writes Aurobindo, “must be judged first by its essential spirit, then by its best accomplishment and, lastly, by its power of survival, renovation and adaptation to new phases of the permanent needs of the race” (64). Indian culture, by virtue of its tolerance and cosmopolitan character, has translated itself into all-embracing human culture. The emerging multiculturalism, though seems to be new, is somewhere an outcome of seeds sown earlier in the form of diversity in ancient times. “Diversity has a meaning and a value. I am one—may I be many—this omnipotent will of the Lord fulfils itself by projecting infinite diversities Indeed, it is the diversity on the surface projected and controlled by the Divine Unity inside that gives rise to the beauty, order and harmony of nature” (*Hinduism at a Glance* 227). There is no denying that, to some extent, the Indian culture is in the grip of Serpentine Western Culture but its spiritual roots and positive viewpoints make protective cover round it against all the polluted forces. It is hoped that it will survive because it teaches how to see “the Eternal One among the many and diverse” resulting in the unity in diversity. Swami Nirvedananda writes: “There may exist diversity of castes, but there must not be any hatred or rancor between them. Each group is sacred. Each has its place and function Each group must have a scope for cultural uplift” (235). Hence, Indian culture is altering its composite design without altering its basic design so that it may cope with the present day multicultural fashion. It has neither left its composite spirit wholly nor embraced multicultural one *in toto*. It lies somewhere in between but its needle gravitates towards multiculturalism.

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